

Mercury-Mercurous Propionate Electrode : Standard Potentials at different Temperatures and related Thermodynamic Quantities in Ethanol-Water Media

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Electromotive force measurements were made of cells of the type,

where $X=10, 20, 30, 45, 60$ and 75 mass% of ethanol at $15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35° . The cell has been used to calculate standard molal potentials (E_m°/V) of the $\text{Hg}/\text{Hg}_2(\text{OPr})_2$, $(\text{OPr})_2$, $(\text{OPr})^-$ electrode and the related thermodynamic quantities for the transfer of HOPr from the aqueous standard state to the standard state in the respective mixed solvents. The values of E_m° as a function of celsius temperature t , in different solvent composition have been determined.

The dependence of the standard potentials at 25° on the dielectric constant of the media (in the light of Born equation), the volume fraction (ϕ_w) and the mole fraction (N_w) of water (based on Feakins-French relationship) has been examined. The variations of the thermodynamic quantities ΔG° , ΔS° and ΔH° with various parameters associated with the solvent media have also been examined.

In a previous work we reported^{1,2} the potentials of the mercury-mercurous propionate electrode and related thermodynamic quantities for the cell reaction in aqueous and dioxan-water media at different temperatures. The present communication is an extension of the same in ethanol-water media. For this purpose the e.m.f. of the cell,

were measured at $15, 20, 25, 30$ and 35° .

Experimental

The materials used, preparation of the electrodes, technique and accuracy of the measurements were the same as described earlier¹. The values of ionisation constants of propionic acid in ethanol-water medium, dielectric constant, density of ethanol-water mixture and other solvent parameters were taken from our earlier work². The measured electromotive forces of the cell corrected to 1 atm pressure of H_2 gas are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—E.M.F. VALUES OF THE CELL (E/V) CORRECTED TO 1 ATM PRESSURE OF H_2 AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

m_1 mol kg ⁻¹	E/V				
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10% Ethanol					
0.090 50	0.858 79	0.861 10	0.863 61	0.867 24	0.869 80
0.078 36	0.861 02	0.862 26	0.865 48	0.869 40	0.872 02
0.066 50	0.864 43	0.866 82	0.869 69	0.872 71	0.876 10
0.043 15	0.874 36	0.876 83	0.880 28	0.883 86	0.886 85
0.031 30	0.880 87	0.883 93	0.887 27	0.890 88	0.893 68
0.024 79	0.886 37	0.889 42	0.892 76	0.896 46	0.899 94
0.018 87	0.893 43	0.896 55	0.900 14	0.903 92	0.907 72
0.012 93	0.901 80	0.905 55	0.908 65	0.913 18	0.916 75
0.007 27	0.917 07	0.919 43	0.923 61	0.927 59	0.932 07
20% Ethanol					
0.093 95	0.858 98	0.861 30	0.864 59	0.864 13	0.867 24
0.083 25	0.860 85	0.863 35	0.866 36	0.866 03	0.869 21
0.076 32	0.861 98	0.864 73	0.867 70	0.867 87	0.871 10
0.051 92	0.870 79	0.873 47	0.887 08	0.876 93	0.879 88
0.042 65	0.875 60	0.878 57	0.881 93	0.881 73	0.885 14
0.030 96	0.882 42	0.885 36	0.889 13	0.888 94	0.892 13
0.023 47	0.888 43	0.892 07	0.895 60	0.895 52	0.899 00
0.015 24	0.899 53	0.902 13	0.906 11	0.906 22	0.910 39
0.010 01	0.901 19	0.912 64	0.916 76	0.917 45	0.920 83
0.004 96	0.925 84	0.929 84	0.934 18	0.934 87	0.939 59

(Table 1 contd.)

30% Ethanol					
0.098 23	0.862 93	0.865 36	0.868 16	0.871 91	0.875 19
0.083 62	0.866 78	0.863 62	0.872 20	0.875 94	0.879 14
0.074 39	0.868 67	0.871 55	0.874 48	0.878 11	0.881 42
0.063 91	0.871 75	0.874 56	0.877 49	0.880 92	0.884 20
0.049 26	0.877 82	0.880 36	0.883 67	0.887 36	0.890 79
0.039 21	0.882 18	0.885 02	0.888 23	0.892 00	0.895 55
0.023 40	0.894 14	0.897 63	0.901 15	0.905 05	0.908 65
0.019 88	0.898 23	0.901 61	0.904 94	0.908 78	0.912 39
0.010 92	0.912 71	0.915 85	0.919 71	0.923 73	0.927 76
45% Ethanol					
0.092 36	0.867 66	0.870 28	0.873 12	0.876 11	0.879 38
0.083 49	0.868 94	0.871 56	0.874 38	0.877 47	0.880 71
0.074 92	0.870 70	0.873 51	0.876 45	0.879 64	0.883 00
0.061 29	0.875 06	0.877 80	0.880 87	0.884 23	0.887 54
0.050 09	0.879 44	0.882 47	0.885 65	0.889 10	0.892 64
0.042 39	0.883 42	0.886 47	0.889 50	0.892 65	0.896 11
0.031 11	0.889 74	0.892 77	0.896 09	0.899 42	0.903 14
0.024 92	0.895 36	0.898 45	0.901 40	0.905 41	0.909 27
0.016 48	0.904 84	0.907 95	0.911 46	0.915 07	0.919 11
0.010 01	0.916 73	0.920 40	0.924 58	0.928 36	0.932 23
60% Ethanol					
0.096 32	0.870 05	0.872 84	0.876 00	0.879 36	0.883 07
0.087 29	0.871 15	0.873 90	0.877 07	0.880 50	0.883 20
0.072 93	0.874 38	0.877 42	0.880 65	0.884 32	0.887 84
0.061 05	0.878 56	0.881 55	0.884 94	0.888 55	0.892 24
0.050 03	0.882 17	0.885 21	0.888 37	0.891 91	0.895 78
0.042 39	0.886 43	0.889 48	0.892 93	0.896 48	0.900 29
0.030 12	0.893 47	0.896 59	0.900 18	0.903 85	0.907 86
0.019 12	0.904 53	0.908 10	0.911 58	0.915 41	0.918 85
0.012 39	0.914 78	0.918 24	0.922 01	0.925 99	0.930 28
0.008 42	0.923 81	0.927 41	0.931 34	0.935 65	0.940 55
75% Ethanol					
0.095 69	0.870 24	0.873 56	0.877 31	0.881 09	0.885 29
0.082 40	0.874 00	0.877 24	0.880 94	0.884 91	0.889 09
0.073 99	0.875 87	0.879 20	0.882 81	0.886 76	0.891 02
0.061 19	0.879 31	0.882 70	0.886 39	0.890 38	0.894 74
0.052 35	0.882 00	0.885 26	0.889 01	0.892 92	0.897 32
0.039 47	0.888 39	0.891 86	0.895 87	0.900 02	0.904 52
0.027 29	0.897 02	0.900 47	0.904 22	0.908 45	0.913 12
0.019 90	0.903 41	0.907 13	0.911 06	0.914 90	0.919 99
0.010 13	0.919 74	0.923 73	0.927 90	0.932 70	0.937 61

Results and Discussion

The cell reaction for the cell (A) is

In the present case, the e.m.f. (*E*) of the cell is given by the equation,

$$E = E_m^0 - K \log K_a - K \log m_u \gamma_u$$

$$= E_m^0 - K \log K_a - K \log (m_1 - m') \gamma_u \quad (1)$$

where $K = (RT/F) \ln 10$ (R = gas constant, T = thermodynamic temperature, F = Faraday constant), m_u is the molality of unionised propionic acid and m' is given quite accurately by $K(m_1/m_2)$ where K_a is the ionisation constant of propionic acid in ethanol-water media, and the values were determined in our laboratory³.

For the buffer solutions (electrolyte solution in the cell) the effect of the salt upon the activity coefficient of propionic acid can be represented by the equation,

$$\log \gamma_u = SI \quad (2)$$

where S is the salting coefficient and I the ionic strength of the electrolyte solution.

The strength of buffer solution was made in such a way that the strengths of HOPr and NaOPr are same. Thus defining,

$$E^0 = E + K \log K_a + K \log (m_1 - m') \quad (3)$$

we have,

$$E^0 = E_m^0 - KSI \quad (4)$$

E^0 was plotted against ionic strength to get the value of E_m^0 . The values of E_m^0 were also determined by method of least-squares with the values of E^0 for different values of I . The standard molal potentials (E_m^0) at various temperatures were fitted, by the method of least-squares, to an equation of the form,

$$E_m^0/V = a^0 + b^0 (t/^\circ C - 25) + c^0 (t/^\circ C - 25)^2 \quad (5)$$

Table 2 presents the values of a^0 , b^0 and c^0 in different ethanol-water media. The values of E_m^0 against different mass % of ethanol at different temperatures are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF THE CONSTANTS OF EQUATION (5)

Ethanol mass %	a^0	$b^0 \times 10^{-4}$	$c^0 \times 10^{-7}$
10	0.498 01	-6 242	2.571 42
20	0.495 27	-5 950	-4 285 70
30	0.482 04	-6 636	-3.428 57
45	0.464 49	-7.420	1.714 28
60	0.446 50	-8.136	2.857 14
75	0.409 25	-9.028	-4 571 42

TABLE 3—STANDARD MOLAL POTENTIALS (E_m^0/V) FOR THE Hg/Hg₂(OPr)₂, OPr⁻ ELECTRODE AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES IN ETHANOL-WATER MEDIA

EtOH mass %	$E_m^0(V)$				
	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°
10	0.504 30	0.501 10	0.498 00	0.494 95	0.491 77
	±0.000 30	±0.000 30	±0.000 30	±0.000 20	±0.000 30
20	0.501 25	0.498 10	0.495 25	0.492 25	0.489 20
	±0.000 30	±0.000 20	±0.000 30	±0.000 20	±0.000 20
30	0.488 68	0.485 28	0.482 03	0.478 80	0.475 33
	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20
45	0.471 94	0.468 19	0.464 49	0.460 81	0.457 08
	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20
60	0.454 67	0.450 57	0.446 52	0.442 23	0.438 40
	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 20	±0.000 30
75	0.418 23	0.413 78	0.409 23	0.404 74	0.400 18
	±0.000 30	±0.000 30	±0.000 30	±0.000 40	±0.000 30

The free energy change (ΔG^0) for the cell reaction in ethanol-water media has been calculated with the equation,

$$\Delta G^0 = -nFE_m^0 \quad (6)$$

The standard enthalpy change for the reaction (ΔH^0) were calculated with the equation,

$$\Delta H^0 = -nF(E_m^0 - T b) \quad (7)$$

and the standard entropy change for the reaction (ΔS^0) with the equation,

$$\Delta S^0 = \frac{\Delta H^0 - \Delta G^0}{T} \quad (8)$$

The values of ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° at 25° in ethanol-water media are given in Table 4.

The Born plot (E_m° vs $1/D$) shows a slight deviation from linearity. Similar deviations were noted in the Born plot for different electrodes in several solvents³⁻⁵, mercury/mercurous acetate electrode^{4,6}.

Fig. 1. Plots of ΔG , ΔS and ΔH against $1/D$.

TABLE 4—VALUES OF DERIVED THERMODYNAMIC QUANTITIES AT 25° IN ETHANOL-WATER MEDIA

EtOH mass %	ΔG° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH° kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
10	-96.102 ± 0.030	-132.017 ± 0.032	-120.5
20	-95.572 ± 0.030	-129.806 ± 0.037	-114.8
30	-93.020 ± 0.019	-131.202 ± 0.023	-128.1
45	-89.636 ± 0.019	-132.328 ± 0.020	-143.2
60	-86.168 ± 0.019	-132.980 ± 0.020	-157.0
75	-78.972 ± 0.030	-130.917 ± 0.031	-174.2

The Feakins and French⁷ plot (E_c° vs $-\log \phi_w$) shows a better linear relationship. The E_c° values, i.e. standard potential on molar scale, were calculated with the equation,

$$E_c^\circ = E_m^\circ + 2K \log d_0$$

where $K = 2.3026 RT/F$ and d_0 is density of the solvent at that temperatures. The density of solvents mixture of ethylalcohol were taken from literature⁸.

The plots of ΔG° , ΔS° and ΔH° for the cell reaction at 25° against $1/D$ were made (Fig. 1). The variation of ΔG° against $1/D$ has been found to increase as the solvent mass % increases. In all the cases, however, the changes in entropy and enthalpy pass through a maximum (nearly at 20 mass % of ethanol).

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